

Geometric Principles for Constructing Free Boundaries in Potential Flows

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Abstract

A complex iterative correction method (CICM) for constructing unknown boundaries in jet flows of an ideal incompressible fluid is developed, based on the combination of the complex variable boundary element method (CVBEM) with the principles of flow rate balance (FRB) and circulation balance (CB). The FRB and CB principles in the natural coordinate system for free streamlines and equipotential lines are formulated and proven.

Keywords: complex variable boundary element method (CVBEM), flow rate balance principle (FRB), circulation balance principle (CB), complex iterative correction method (CICM), ideal fluid jet theory, complex potential, Cauchy-type integral.

1 Introduction

In the theory of jet, cavitation and wave flows of an ideal incompressible fluid, the presence of unknown boundaries is a source of significant mathematical difficulties in constructing and analyzing solutions. The formulation and solution of the first jet problems were carried out by Helmholtz and Kirchhoff in the mid-19th century [1,2]. The fruitful idea of applying the theory of functions of a complex variable in fluid mechanics also belongs to Kirchhoff. Since then, this area of fluid mechanics has been actively developed by the works of many outstanding scientists worldwide. The rapid development of this topic led to the exhaustion of problems amenable to analytical solution, and the rapid improvement of computing technology prompted researchers to create corresponding numerical methods [1,3,4,5].

2 Complex Variable Boundary Element Method

2.1 Description of CVBEM

The Cauchy integral formula and the Cauchy-type integral constitute the main theoretical premise for numerical studies of boundary value problems of the theory of analytic functions using CVBEM [3,4,6]. A distinctive feature of many fluid mechanics problems is that on each part of the flow boundary either the real or the imaginary component of an analytic function (complex potential) is known. Such problems are called mixed boundary value problems of the theory of analytic functions.

The complex variable boundary element method allows solving the following problem.

Let there be some region Ω on the plane, bounded by a polygon (Fig.1). For simplicity, we assume the region is simply connected (although in general this is not necessary). At each node of the polygon, either only the value of the real part of the analytic function $w = w(z)$ or only its imaginary part is known. It is necessary to restore the missing information. In other words, if the value of the real part is known at a node, then the value of the imaginary part needs to be determined. If the value of the imaginary part is known at a node, then the value of the real part needs to be determined.

It is important to note that the function $w = w(z)$ itself is unknown to us; we only know that it is analytic. CVBEM allows, after restoring the missing values of the analytic function, to restore the function itself (approximately, but with any accuracy that depends on the number of nodes).

In CVBEM, the value of the analytic function is denoted by a bar over the symbol:

$$\bar{w}_j = \bar{\varphi}_j + i\bar{\psi}_j$$

is the value of the analytic function $w = w(z)$ at node j . The concept of an approximation function, denoted by a hat $\hat{w}(z_k)$, is also introduced. The contour is traversed so that the region remains on the left.

For each node, the approximation function must be written:

$$\hat{w}(z_k) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \bar{w}_k \ln \left(\frac{z_{k+1} - z_k}{z_{k-1} - z_k} \right) + \frac{1}{2\pi i} \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq k, j \neq k-1}}^m \left[\left(\frac{z_k - z_j}{z_{j+1} - z_j} \bar{w}_{j+1} - \frac{z_k - z_{j+1}}{z_{j+1} - z_j} \bar{w}_j \right) \ln \left(\frac{z_{j+1} - z_k}{z_j - z_k} \right) \right]$$

The approximation function can also be presented in the form used in programming the method:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{w}(z_k) = & \frac{1}{2\pi i} \bar{w}_k \ln \left| \frac{z_{k+1} - z_k}{z_{k-1} - z_k} \right| + \frac{\bar{w}_k}{2\pi} \left(\arg(z_{k+1} - z_k) - \arg(z_{k-1} - z_k) \right) \\ & + \frac{1}{2\pi i} \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq k, j \neq k-1}}^m \left[\left(\frac{z_k - z_j}{z_{j+1} - z_j} \bar{w}_{j+1} - \frac{z_k - z_{j+1}}{z_{j+1} - z_j} \bar{w}_j \right) \ln \left(\frac{z_{j+1} - z_k}{z_j - z_k} \right) \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$0 \leq \arg(z_{k+1} - z_k) < 2\pi, \quad 0 \leq \arg(z_{k-1} - z_k) < 2\pi$$

$$\arg(z_{k+1} - z_k) - \arg(z_{k-1} - z_k) = \begin{cases} \arg(z_{k+1} - z_k) - \arg(z_{k-1} - z_k), \\ \text{if } \arg(z_{k+1} - z_k) - \arg(z_{k-1} - z_k) > 0 \\ \\ 2\pi + \arg(z_{k+1} - z_k) - \arg(z_{k-1} - z_k), \\ \text{if } \arg(z_{k+1} - z_k) - \arg(z_{k-1} - z_k) < 0 \end{cases}$$

Figure 1: Discretization of the domain boundary into boundary elements

First, it is necessary to write the approximation function for each boundary node, keeping the expression $\bar{w}_j = \bar{\varphi}_j + i\bar{\psi}_j$ in symbolic form, and replacing the node coordinates with their numerical values. Separating now the real and imaginary parts, we obtain a system of linear algebraic equations (SLAE) with respect to the unknown components $\bar{w}_j = \bar{\varphi}_j + i\bar{\psi}_j$. This system has the form $AX + iBX = 0$, where matrices A and B are real with size $m \times 2m$ (m rows and $2m$ columns), and the column matrix $X = X(\bar{\varphi}_1, \bar{\psi}_1, \bar{\varphi}_2, \bar{\psi}_2, \dots, \bar{\varphi}_m, \bar{\psi}_m)$ contains the known and unknown components $\bar{w}_j = \bar{\varphi}_j + i\bar{\psi}_j$.

By subsequently separating the real and imaginary parts and substituting the numerical value for the symbol $\bar{w}_j = \bar{\varphi}_j + i\bar{\psi}_j$, we arrive at a real SLAE, from the solution of which the missing values $\bar{w}_j = \bar{\varphi}_j + i\bar{\psi}_j$ at the nodal points are determined.

Now, knowing all values $\bar{w}_j = \bar{\varphi}_j + i\bar{\psi}_j$, the analytic function itself (complex potential) can be restored by the formula:

$$w(z) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \sum_{j=1}^m \left[\left(\frac{z - z_j}{z_{j+1} - z_j} \bar{w}_{j+1} - \frac{z - z_{j+1}}{z_{j+1} - z_j} \bar{w}_j \right) \ln \left(\frac{z_{j+1} - z}{z_j - z} \right) \right]$$

2.2 Modified CVBEM

The complex variable boundary element method is applicable to any single-valued analytic function of a complex variable. One such function in hydrodynamics is the complex conjugate velocity $W(z) = v_x(x, y) - iv_y(x, y)$. A specific feature of many hydrodynamics problems with an unknown boundary is that on some parts of the boundary the normal velocity component v_n is known, while on others the tangential component v_s is known. Taking this feature into account, the Cauchy integral formula can be written as:

$$W(z_0) = (v_n(z_0) - iv_s(z_0)) e^{-i\alpha(z_0)} = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{\Gamma} \frac{(v_n(z) - iv_s(z)) e^{-i\alpha(z)}}{z - z_0} dz$$

In this formula, the angle α is the angle between the outward normal to the region and the abscissa axis.

Further, everything is done by analogy with the above. For each node of the region, the approximation function is written:

$$\widehat{W}(z_k) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \overline{W}_k \ln \left| \frac{z_{k+1} - z_k}{z_{k-1} - z_k} \right| + \frac{\overline{W}_k}{2\pi} (\arg(z_{k+1} - z_k) - \arg(z_{k-1} - z_k))$$

$$+ \frac{1}{2\pi i} \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq k, j \neq k-1}}^m \left[\left(\frac{z_k - z_j}{z_{j+1} - z_j} \overline{W}_{j+1} - \frac{z_k - z_{j+1}}{z_{j+1} - z_j} \overline{W}_j \right) \ln \left(\frac{z_{j+1} - z_k}{z_j - z_k} \right) \right]$$

$$0 \leq \arg(z_{k+1} - z_k) < 2\pi, \quad 0 \leq \arg(z_{k-1} - z_k) < 2\pi$$

$$\arg(z_{k+1} - z_k) - \arg(z_{k-1} - z_k) = \begin{cases} \arg(z_{k+1} - z_k) - \arg(z_{k-1} - z_k), \\ \text{if } \arg(z_{k+1} - z_k) - \arg(z_{k-1} - z_k) > 0 \\ 2\pi + \arg(z_{k+1} - z_k) - \arg(z_{k-1} - z_k), \\ \text{if } \arg(z_{k+1} - z_k) - \arg(z_{k-1} - z_k) < 0 \end{cases}$$

$$\overline{W}_j = \overline{v}_{nj} \exp(-\overline{\alpha}_j) - i \overline{v}_{sj} \exp(-\overline{\alpha}_j)$$

$$\exp(-\overline{\alpha}_j) = \cos(\overline{\alpha}_j) - i \sin(\overline{\alpha}_j)$$

$$\sin(\overline{\alpha}_j) = \text{Im} \left[-i \frac{z_{j+1} - z_j}{|z_{j+1} - z_j|} \right], \quad \cos(\overline{\alpha}_j) = \text{Re} \left[-i \frac{z_{j+1} - z_j}{|z_{j+1} - z_j|} \right]$$

Separating similarly the real and imaginary parts, we obtain a system of linear algebraic equations $AX + iBX = 0$. Here, the column matrix $X = X(\overline{v}_{n1}, \overline{v}_{s1}, \overline{v}_{n2}, \overline{v}_{s2}, \dots, \overline{v}_{nm}, \overline{v}_{sm})$. Repeated separation of real and imaginary parts allows obtaining the matrix equation $GY = F$. Matrix G and the right-hand side vector F are obtained according to the following rule [4]: if at node z_j the tangential velocity component \overline{v}_{sj} is given, then the j -th row of matrix B is taken, and after selecting the row elements corresponding to unknown values \overline{v}_s or \overline{v}_n at all other nodes, the j -th row of matrix G is obtained. The j -th element of vector Y will be \overline{v}_{nj} , the j -th element of vector F is the sum of known values \overline{v}_s or \overline{v}_n multiplied by the corresponding elements of matrix B . If at node z_j the normal velocity component \overline{v}_{nj} is given, then to construct the j -th row of matrix G , matrix A is used.

Then the complex conjugate velocity $W(z)$ itself can be found by the formula:

$$W(z) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \sum_{j=1}^m \left[\left(\frac{z - z_j}{z_{j+1} - z_j} \overline{W}_{j+1} - \frac{z - z_{j+1}}{z_{j+1} - z_j} \overline{W}_j \right) \ln \left(\frac{z_{j+1} - z}{z_j - z} \right) \right]$$

The complex potential of the flow $w(z)$ is determined up to a complex constant, which has no physical meaning and can be set to zero. Taking this into account, the complex potential of the flow $w(z)$ is found by integrating the last expression for the complex conjugate velocity $W(z)$: $w(z) = \int_0^z W(z) dz$.

3 Geometric Principles

3.1 Flow Rate Balance Principle

Figure 2: a) Boundary element; b) Computational domain

On the free boundary of the jet (free streamlines) A_3A_4 and A_5A_6 , the velocity magnitude is constant $v_s = \pm v_0 = \pm 1$ (the sign depends on the choice of direction of the natural coordinate system axes), and the normal velocity component is zero $v_n = 0$. On lines of equal potential A_2A_3 and A_6A_1 , the tangential velocity component is zero $v_s = 0$, and the normal velocity component takes a constant value $v_n = \pm 1$. This feature of the problem makes its consideration more convenient in the natural coordinate system (\vec{n}, \vec{s}) . It is known [8] that with the introduction of the natural coordinate system adopted here (Fig.2), the following relations (Cauchy-Riemann conditions) hold:

$$v_n = \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial n} = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial s}; \quad v_s = \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial s} = -\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial n}$$

Let

$$\psi = \psi(n, s) = \psi(n(x, y), s(x, y))$$

Then, using the invariance property of the form of the first differential and the Cauchy-Riemann conditions, we can write:

$$dn = \frac{\partial n}{\partial x} dx + \frac{\partial n}{\partial y} dy; \quad ds = \frac{\partial s}{\partial x} dx + \frac{\partial s}{\partial y} dy$$

$$\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial n} \frac{\partial n}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial x}; \quad \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial n} \frac{\partial n}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial y}$$

$$\begin{aligned} d\psi &= \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} dx + \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y} dy = \left(\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial n} \frac{\partial n}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial x} \right) dx + \left(\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial n} \frac{\partial n}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial y} \right) dy \\ &= \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial n} \left(\frac{\partial n}{\partial x} dx + \frac{\partial n}{\partial y} dy \right) + \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial s} \left(\frac{\partial s}{\partial x} dx + \frac{\partial s}{\partial y} dy \right) = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial n} dn + \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial s} ds = -v_s dn + v_n ds \end{aligned}$$

Along the free streamlines A_3A_4 and A_5A_6 , the stream function $\psi = \psi(n, s) = \text{Const}$ remains constant and $d\psi = 0$. This allows formulating the **flow rate balance principle (FRB)** for a streamline:

$$v_s dn = v_n ds \quad (*)$$

This relation can be written in discrete form: $v_{sj}\Delta n_j = v_{nj}\Delta s_j$, where $\Delta s_j = |\Delta \vec{s}_j| = |z_{j+1} - z_j| = |\Gamma_j|$.

The relation $v_s dn = v_n ds$ will be called the flow rate balance principle, since $d\psi = dQ = 0$ along a streamline. In this formula, Q denotes the flow rate.

3.2 Circulation Balance Principle

Now assuming that

$$\varphi = \varphi(n, s) = \varphi(n(x, y), s(x, y))$$

Similarly to the previous, we can write:

$$dn = \frac{\partial n}{\partial x} dx + \frac{\partial n}{\partial y} dy; \quad ds = \frac{\partial s}{\partial x} dx + \frac{\partial s}{\partial y} dy$$

$$\frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial n} \frac{\partial n}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial x}; \quad \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial n} \frac{\partial n}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial y}$$

$$\begin{aligned} d\varphi &= \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial x} dx + \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial y} dy = \left(\frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial n} \frac{\partial n}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial x} \right) dx + \left(\frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial n} \frac{\partial n}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial y} \right) dy \\ &= \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial n} \left(\frac{\partial n}{\partial x} dx + \frac{\partial n}{\partial y} dy \right) + \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial s} \left(\frac{\partial s}{\partial x} dx + \frac{\partial s}{\partial y} dy \right) = \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial n} dn + \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial s} ds = v_n dn + v_s ds \end{aligned}$$

Along the lines of equal potential A_2A_3 and A_6A_1 , the function $\varphi = \varphi(n, s) = \text{Const}$ remains constant and $d\varphi = 0$. This allows formulating the **circulation balance principle (CBP)** for an equipotential line:

$$v_n dn = -v_s ds \quad (**)$$

This relation can be written in discrete form: $v_{nj}\Delta n_j = -v_{sj}\Delta s_j$, where $\Delta s_j = |\Delta \vec{s}_j| = |z_{j+1} - z_j| = |\Gamma_j|$.

The relation $v_n dn = -v_s ds$ will be appropriately called the circulation balance principle, since $d\varphi = d\Gamma = 0$ along an equipotential line. Here Γ denotes circulation.

3.3 Point Displacement Rules

The unknown jet boundaries are initially specified arbitrarily and then corrected using the formulas:

$$x'_j = x_j + \Delta x_j, \quad y'_j = y_j + \Delta y_j$$

where x'_j, y'_j are the new coordinates, x_j, y_j are the old coordinates, $\Delta x_j, \Delta y_j$ are the displacements of points on the unknown boundary.

Let us establish formulas for the displacements $\Delta x_j, \Delta y_j$. Let \vec{s}_j be the unit tangent vector drawn to the boundary element Γ_j at point z_j , and \vec{n}_j be the unit normal vector drawn at the same point (Fig.2). In this case, the equality holds:

$$\vec{n}_j = -i \vec{s}_j = -i \frac{z_{j+1} - z_j}{|z_{j+1} - z_j|} = -i \frac{(x_{j+1} + iy_{j+1}) - (x_j + iy_j)}{|\Delta \vec{s}_j|} = \frac{(y_{j+1} - y_j) - i(x_{j+1} - x_j)}{\Delta s_j}$$

Multiply this vector equality by the number Δn_j :

$$\Delta n_j \vec{n}_j = \delta \vec{n}_j = \frac{\Delta n_j (y_{j+1} - y_j) - i \Delta n_j (x_{j+1} - x_j)}{\Delta s_j}$$

This vector equality is equivalent to two scalar equalities:

$$\Delta x_j = \delta n_{jx} = \frac{\Delta n_j}{\Delta s_j} (y_{j+1} - y_j) \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta y_j = \delta n_{jy} = -\frac{\Delta n_j}{\Delta s_j} (x_{j+1} - x_j).$$

Assuming that the displaced points belong to a streamline, we express from the flow rate balance principle the ratio $\frac{\Delta n_j}{\Delta s_j} = \frac{v_{nj}}{v_{sj}}$ and substitute it into the two previous equalities:

$$\Delta x_j = \frac{v_{nj}}{v_{sj}} (y_{j+1} - y_j) \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta y_j = -\frac{v_{nj}}{v_{sj}} (x_{j+1} - x_j).$$

These equalities allow displacing points lying on an unknown streamline under the condition that the velocity is directed along the unit tangent vector (streamline A_5A_6 (Fig.2b)). If the direction of the velocity and the unit tangent vector do not coincide, then it is necessary to use the formulas (streamline A_3A_4 (Fig.2b)):

$$\Delta x_j = -\frac{v_{nj}}{v_{sj}} (y_{j+1} - y_j) \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta y_j = \frac{v_{nj}}{v_{sj}} (x_{j+1} - x_j).$$

Points lying on an equipotential line must be displaced along the tangent.

$$\vec{s}_j = \frac{z_{j+1} - z_j}{|z_{j+1} - z_j|} = \frac{(x_{j+1} + iy_{j+1}) - (x_j + iy_j)}{|\Delta \vec{s}_j|} = \frac{(x_{j+1} - x_j) + i(y_{j+1} - y_j)}{\Delta s_j}$$

Multiply this vector equality by the number Δn_j :

$$\Delta n_j \vec{s}_j = \delta \vec{s}_j = \frac{\Delta n_j (x_{j+1} - x_j) + i \Delta n_j (y_{j+1} - y_j)}{\Delta s_j}$$

Through similar reasoning using the circulation balance principle for an equipotential line ($\frac{\Delta n_j}{\Delta s_j} = -\frac{v_{sj}}{v_{nj}}$), the formulas can be obtained:

$$\Delta x_j = -\frac{v_{sj}}{v_{nj}} (x_{j+1} - x_j) \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta y_j = -\frac{v_{sj}}{v_{nj}} (y_{j+1} - y_j).$$

These equalities allow displacing points lying on an equipotential line under the condition that the velocity is directed against the unit normal vector (equipotential A_4A_5 (Fig.2b)). This equipotential corresponds to the input boundary of the jet. However, these equalities are not used because the input boundary of the jet is considered known. The solid wall A_1A_2 is also considered given.

For the output boundaries (equipotentials A_1A_6 and A_2A_3 (Fig.2b)), the displacement formulas have the form:

$$\Delta x_j = \frac{v_{sj}}{v_{nj}} (x_{j+1} - x_j) \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta y_j = \frac{v_{sj}}{v_{nj}} (y_{j+1} - y_j).$$

4 Calculation Results

The modified CVBEM allows, by specifying only one velocity component v_{nj} or v_{sj} at points on the boundary of domain Ω , to obtain the missing components. The corresponding displacement formulas, obtained based on the flow rate and circulation balance principles, allow zeroing the normal velocity component on streamlines and the tangential

velocity component on equipotential lines. In the conditions of this problem, the velocity components were specified as follows: on the solid wall A_1A_2 $v_n = 0$ (no-penetration condition), on equipotentials A_2A_3 and A_6A_1 $v_n = 1$ (output boundaries), on streamline A_3A_4 $v_s = -1$, on streamline A_5A_6 $v_s = 1$, on equipotential A_4A_5 $v_n = -1$ (input boundary). From the found values of the velocity components, the function $W(z) = v_x(x, y) - iv_y(x, y)$ can be restored and then the complex potential of the flow $w(z) = \int_0^z W(z)dz$ can be constructed. By calculating the values of the function $w(z)$ at points of interest in the domain, internal streamlines and lines of equal potential can be constructed using the methodology [7] (Fig.3).

Figure 3: Streamlines and equipotential lines for various jet impingement angles

5 Conclusion

A complex iterative correction method for constructing unknown boundaries of plane jet flows of an ideal fluid has been developed, based on the combination of CVBEM with FRB and CBP. The FRB and CBP in the natural coordinate system for free streamlines and equipotential lines have been formulated and proven. Formulas for successive displacements of points located on unknown boundaries have been obtained. These formulas are convenient because they do not contain the quantities Δn_j and Δs_j , but use only velocity components. Thus, the quantities Δn_j and Δs_j are not computed, which reduces the program's running time. Using the proposed method, the solution to the classical problem of a jet impinging on an infinite wall has been constructed for four values of the impingement angle. In each case, streamlines and equipotential lines have been constructed. It should be noted that a distinctive feature of the method is the possibility of constructing the complex potential of the flow.

APPENDIX

It is known that plane flow of an ideal incompressible fluid of variable density is described in terms of the velocity potential and stream function satisfying the equations:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\rho(x, y) \frac{\partial \varphi(x, y)}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\rho(x, y) \frac{\partial \varphi(x, y)}{\partial y} \right) = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{1}{\rho(x, y)} \frac{\partial \psi(x, y)}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\frac{1}{\rho(x, y)} \frac{\partial \psi(x, y)}{\partial y} \right) = 0$$

These equations are no longer Laplace equations; they are sometimes called generalized Laplace equations. The generalized Cauchy-Riemann conditions in the Cartesian coordinate system are also valid:

$$v_x(x, y) = \frac{\partial \varphi(x, y)}{\partial x} = \frac{1}{\rho(x, y)} \frac{\partial \psi(x, y)}{\partial y}$$

$$v_y(x, y) = \frac{\partial \varphi(x, y)}{\partial y} = -\frac{1}{\rho(x, y)} \frac{\partial \psi(x, y)}{\partial x}$$

Generalized Cauchy-Riemann conditions in the natural coordinate system:

$$v_n(x, y) = \frac{\partial \varphi(n, s)}{\partial n} = \frac{1}{\rho(x, y)} \frac{\partial \psi(n, s)}{\partial s}$$

$$v_s(x, y) = \frac{\partial \varphi(n, s)}{\partial s} = -\frac{1}{\rho(x, y)} \frac{\partial \psi(n, s)}{\partial n}$$

Write the total differential of the stream function $\psi = \psi(n, s) = \psi(n(x, y), s(x, y))$ in the natural coordinate system:

$$d\psi(n, s) = \frac{\partial \psi(n, s)}{\partial n} dn + \frac{\partial \psi(n, s)}{\partial s} ds$$

From the generalized Cauchy-Riemann conditions we obtain:

$$\frac{\partial \psi(n, s)}{\partial s} = \rho(x, y) v_n(x, y)$$

$$\frac{\partial \psi(n, s)}{\partial n} = -\rho(x, y) v_s(x, y)$$

Substitute these equalities into the expression for the total differential:

$$d\psi(n, s) = \frac{\partial \psi(n, s)}{\partial n} dn + \frac{\partial \psi(n, s)}{\partial s} ds = -\rho(x, y) v_s(x, y) dn + \rho(x, y) v_n(x, y) ds$$

$$= \rho(x, y) (v_n(x, y) ds - v_s(x, y) dn)$$

Considering that along the free boundary $d\psi(n, s) = 0$, we obtain:

$$\rho(x, y) (v_n(x, y) ds - v_s(x, y) dn) = 0$$

Or after canceling the density: $v_n(x, y) ds - v_s(x, y) dn = 0$.

The equality $v_n(x, y) ds = v_s(x, y) dn$ coincides with the previously obtained equality (*) for an ideal fluid of constant density.

Similarly, we obtain equality from considering the total differential of the velocity potential function. Write the total differential of the velocity potential function $\varphi = \varphi(n, s) = \varphi(n(x, y), s(x, y))$ in the natural coordinate system:

$$d\varphi(n, s) = \frac{\partial\varphi(n, s)}{\partial n}dn + \frac{\partial\varphi(n, s)}{\partial s}ds$$

From the generalized Cauchy-Riemann conditions we obtain:

$$\frac{\partial\varphi(n, s)}{\partial n} = v_n(x, y)$$

$$\frac{\partial\varphi(n, s)}{\partial s} = v_s(x, y)$$

Substitute these equalities into the expression for the total differential:

$$d\varphi(n, s) = \frac{\partial\varphi(n, s)}{\partial n}dn + \frac{\partial\varphi(n, s)}{\partial s}ds = v_n(x, y)dn + v_s(x, y)ds$$

Considering that along an equipotential line $d\varphi(n, s) = 0$, we obtain:

$$v_n(x, y)dn + v_s(x, y)ds = 0$$

The equality $v_n(x, y)dn = -v_s(x, y)ds$ coincides with the previously obtained equality (**) for an ideal fluid of constant density.

The considered example shows that relations (*) and (**) hold not only in an ideal fluid of constant density, but have a more general character. It can be shown that these relations remain valid for plane potential flow of an ideal gas. The CVBEM solver is only suitable for the Laplace equation, so in the case of more complex equations, it should be replaced, for example, with the finite element method (FEM). The proposed principles for constructing free boundaries remain unchanged. Moreover, the obtained relations can be easily modified if a more complex condition is specified on the boundary (presence of gravity or capillarity).

References

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